

Research paper

Islanders' perceptions of innovative energy solutions before and after engaging in energy transition projects

Fausto Sainz Salces^a, Andrew Barney^{b,*}, Heracles Polatidis^b

^a International University of La Rioja, College of Engineering and Technology (ESIT), Avenida de la Paz, 137, Logroño 26006, Spain

^b Uppsala University, Dept. of Earth Sciences, Cramérsgatan 3, Visby 621 57, Sweden

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ABSTRACT

The transition to renewable and smart energy systems is critical to address climate change and reduced energy security, particularly on islands where the negative impacts of both are already being felt. This transition, however, is being delayed by, among others, the lack of islanders' awareness of the effective use of potential energy transition technologies and practices. This paper studies island residents' initial awareness and knowledge of energy concepts and technologies, before their interaction with them in the context of the four-year EU Horizon 2020 REACT (Renewable Energy for Self-Sustainable Islands) project. Three European islands, Inis Mór (Ireland), La Graciosa (Spain), and San Pietro (Italy) are studied. The analysis seeks to determine how individual's initial levels of awareness impacted perceived experiences, usability and desire to continue using REACT's suggested energy transition solutions, technologies and software.

The study employed interviews, Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) surveys, and System Usability Scale (SUS) surveys, to evaluate and assess the REACT's project participants' attitudes and awareness towards the project's energy transition concepts and tools. Interviews were conducted before participants interacted with any energy transition technology or software and provided insights into participants' initial knowledge, awareness and attitudes while the TAM and SUS surveys were conducted after the participants had interacted with the REACT's proposed technologies and evaluated their perceived usefulness, ease of use, and overall user experience.

Results showed that a participant's initial awareness and knowledge had influenced their experiences with the deployed energy transition technologies, both positively and negatively. Despite these differing experiences, most participants, regardless of initial awareness and knowledge level, found the technologies relatively useful and expressed a willingness to continue using them.

The paper's findings underline the importance of understanding participants' starting points in terms of awareness and knowledge when planning and implementing energy transition activities. Energy planners seeking to involve people in the energy transition should work to address low levels of awareness and knowledge before beginning, such as with additional information and training tailored to their potential participants' starting points. In doing so, energy transition planners and energy project developers and managers can enhance participants' experiences with transition activities and foster long-term engagement.

1. Introduction

As the realities of climate change and diminishing energy security are becoming clearer, the need to transition away from fossil fuel energy sources and instead use renewable, reliable and, if possible, local energy sources becomes ever more apparent. This need to transition has been progressing around the world but is of critical importance on islands where many of climate change's impacts are already being felt

(Storlazzi, et al., 2018; IPCC, 2023). As a recognition of this, many energy transition pilot projects have been funded and undertaken on islands, particularly in Europe (European Commission, 2017; European Commission, 2018), where combinations of different renewable energy sources, energy storage, management solutions and smart energy networks have been implemented (Gift H2020, 2023; Insulae h2020, 2023; SMILE, 2023; MAESHA, 2023).

Significant research has been devoted to the study of public perception of and experience with large scale renewable energy

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: andrew.barney@geo.uu.se (A. Barney).

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Nomenclature

SUS	System Usability Scale
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model

technologies (supply side of the energy system) like wind turbines, solar PV parks, hydro projects and the associated infrastructure like transmission lines and grid expansion (Horbaty, et al., 2012; Delicado, et al., 2015; Cousse, 2021) but less has been done in regards to the actual use, perception and individual attitudes towards home energy technologies (demand side of the energy system) (Li, et al., 2017; Parrish, et al., 2020; Pratt and Erickson, 2020), like demand response devices and smart residential energy applications and users' responses via software apps. This is especially important for islands, where demand side management plays an even greater role in their energy systems due to their (semi) autonomy from the main land grid. This paper examines residential and community building energy transition technology users in different islands' situations and studies their attitudes and experience before and after the use of such technologies.

To this end, a number of island residents were interviewed regarding their initial understanding of and attitudes towards different energy transition technologies and concepts in order to illustrate their prior knowledge and perceptions. These same individuals, then, had a combination of energy transition technologies, roof mounted solar PV panels, heat pumps, batteries and related energy demand software, installed at their homes or at a building they managed. Approximately a year after these technologies had been installed and used, the residents were asked to respond to a Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and a System Usability Scale (SUS) survey to evaluate their actual experience when using these technologies and to assess whether their initial attitudes and understandings had any discernible bearing on their experiences with the software and the technologies deployed and how it could be of impact in future energy transition activities both on islands and beyond.

Knowing where islanders are in their understandings and awareness of energy transition is helpful to island energy planners when developing local policies (Betti, et al., 2022), as research has shown that a lack of awareness can pose a significant hindrance to energy transition activities (Liu, et al., 2013; Bugden and Stedman, 2019; Biresselioglu, et al., 2020). To further these understandings, this paper depicts islanders' perceptions of innovative energy solutions before and after engaging in energy transition projects. To our knowledge, this is the first such paper that does so on islands and provides new insights on the differences between islanders living in different climatic zones, policy conditions, communities and energy systems.

The key contributions of this paper are to increase knowledge of:

- whether initial islanders' attitudes and understandings impact their user experience with developed energy management software/tools and deployed energy transition technologies
- the changes in islanders' perceptions towards key energy transition concepts and activities from their involvement in an energy transition project
- whether islanders' participation with developed tools and deployed transition technologies established support and long-term engagement

These contributions have been reached using interview and survey responses from participants in the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation project REACT (Renewable Energy for Self-Sustainable Islands) (REACT, 2019) and the specific (Pilot) islands considered in this work are Inis Mór, Ireland, La Graciosa, Spain and San Pietro, Italy. The islands selected for inclusion in the REACT project were of differing

sizes and had varying local climates and policy environments to provide as wide a cross section on EU island conditions as possible (Barney, et al., 2021, 2022). The technologies deployed varied by island and included solar PV panels, batteries and heat pumps that were installed at private and public buildings. The participants on these islands also received a project developed app which provided information on the deployed technologies and participant energy consumption behaviors (European Commission, 2019; European Commission, 2021).

The structure of the paper is as follows: Chapter 2 provides a literature review on perceptions on and acceptance for energy transition and highlights how understandings and attitudes impact user experiences. Chapter 3 describes the methodologies applied for the interviews and surveys and then for the analysis of the responses. Chapter 4 details the results from each of the islands' considered for the interviews and surveys and includes discussion on those results. Chapter 5 provides the overall conclusions from the paper's findings.

2. Perceptions on energy transition and its acceptance

Beyond their vulnerability to the impacts of climate change (Storlazzi, et al., 2018; IPCC, 2023), there are additional reasons for geographic islands to work on transitioning away from a reliance on fossil fuel-based electricity and heating systems. These include goals of achieving energy independence and increasing energy security by minimizing the disruptable and costly energy supplies obtained from the mainland. Despite incentives to transition, and plentiful local renewable energy sources, the energy transition faces barriers. Not all of these barriers are unique to islands, and can include uncertainty for which rules apply to the activities being undertaken (Biresselioglu, et al., 2020) misalignments between policy and planning (Zepa, 2022; Marcinkowska, et al., 2022) as well as a simple lack of awareness (Parrish, et al., 2020), but they can be worsened by the isolation many islands find themselves in.

Further, islands encounter additional challenges in their transition compared to mainland energy systems, such as higher costs and more difficulty in balancing energy systems (Basir Khan, et al., 2014; Blechinger, et al., 2016; Jelić, et al., 2020). The lack of uniformity of island energy systems further requires recognition and accommodation in high level policies created to encourage energy transition (Clean energy for EU islands secretariat, 2023). Moreover, deployments of renewable energy technologies on islands are further complicated by limited space and the resulting land use conflicts (Cardinaletti and Di Perna, 2009) which must be evaluated and addressed on an island-by-island basis (Clean energy for EU islands secretariat, 2023).

At the individual level, people are, for the most part, aware of climate change (Whitmarsh and Capstick, 2018) and of the need for energy transition to take place. However, this high level of awareness disappears as individuals are questioned about the specific actions, tools and measures that need to be undertaken to achieve that transition (Komendantova, 2021; Betti, et al., 2022). The resulting lack of awareness in these specifics has been identified as a roadblock to their wider uptake (Liu, et al., 2013; Bugden and Stedman, 2019; Biresselioglu, et al., 2020; Gohary, et al., 2022), which is a clear concern for a successful transition where individuals are expected to take key roles in the transition (Stephanides, et al., 2019). It has been further noted that existing awareness of, and perceptions on, energy transition related technologies can impact attitudes towards the technologies' perceived usefulness, ease of use (Kardooni, et al., 2016), and individuals' willingness to support them (Gaede, et al., 2020). Conversely, the risk perception of technologies is reduced when technologies are used or individuals are otherwise exposed to them (Osazuwa-Peters, et al., 2020; Linzenich, et al., 2020) and awareness and knowledge impact the uptake of technologies (Billanes and Enevoldsen, 2021) which, taken together, underscore the importance of building an understanding of the feedback between awareness and willingness of individuals to engage, and continue to engage, with transition technologies.

The correct use of devices and technology that help in the electricity management of various dwellings can improve and encourage changes in electricity use habits. That said, how a user decides to behave with these is crucial for the adoption of energy management technology, meaning successful energy transitions are dependent on households using those technologies to support the energy system, and research has found that the mere installation of a technology does not guarantee its initial or continuing use (Hargreaves, et al., 2013, 2017; Buchanan, et al., 2014; Herrero, et al., 2018; Li, et al., 2021). At the same time, improving perceived performance of a technology, such as increasing efficiency or reducing environmental impact (Demski, et al., 2015), is an important factor in a user’s likelihood to use and continue using a technology (Hubert, et al., 2019; Chadwick and Russell-Bennett, 2022).

With all that in mind, the REACT project’s software was developed to be easily adopted so users could quickly use it without requiring prior experience with other applications (Carrillo, et al., 2017). The methodological approach to the design of the interface for the REACT software followed an inclusive design approach that aims to reach a balance between modelling complexity and interpretability and usability. This was also complemented with the need to create an interface that accommodates the specific user-needs (Savidis and Stephanidis, 2004; Chang, et al., 2021).

Further, prior to the interviews conducted in this paper, residents of the project’s three Pilot islands were initially surveyed to determine how prepared the islanders were to engage with demand response and related energy technologies as well as their motivations for engaging in energy transition projects. This prior survey found that the respondents on these islands expressed a high degree of motivation to participate in energy transition projects and activities. It was further found that these respondents generally had very low levels of awareness around several of the key elements of the planned REACT project and the activities expected to be carried out on their islands (Abi Ghanem and Crosbie, 2021).

Understanding how much awareness and experience a project’s participants have with whatever is being implemented by a project is important in helping to understand their experiences, can potentially

allow project managers and planners to guide interactions, support uptake and continued use of what is being tested as well as improve the overall outcomes of the project (Barney, et al., 2023). This is especially true for projects seeking to test technologies and software tools advancing energy transition (Hargreaves, et al., 2013; Williams, et al., 2020). The information gathered before, after and during the deployment of the REACT project’s developed software and the installed technologies, provides an opportunity to gain additional knowledge on participants’ positions and if these created barriers or pathways for adaptation, something of keen interest to the broader energy transition.

3. Methods

Three different methods were used in this paper to evaluate REACT project Pilot islands’ participants’ initial awareness and understanding of energy concepts and techniques, the islanders’ perceived usability of the REACT technologies and tools and the islanders’ willingness to continue using them (Fig. 1).

The first of these methods were interviews while the second and third of these were Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989) and System Usability Scale (SUS) (Brooke, 1996) surveys. A broad range of qualitative information on participants’ starting attitudes and understandings were gathered from the initial interviews. The usage of the following two surveys provided a more focused, streamlined evaluation of the islanders’ perceived usability of the REACT technologies and tools (Pal and Vanijja, 2020) at two different points in the project. Using these different assessment approaches together provided a range of information on changes in participant starting positions, as identified in the interviews, while also allowing an assessment of their willingness to continue to engage with the deployed technologies and tools.

All those interviewed and surveyed were islander participants in the REACT project and had been selected to take part in the REACT Pilot islands technology deployments as either dwelling owners or managers of public buildings. Further, these participants had been interacting with the REACT solutions prior to the TAM and SUS surveys taking place.

A limitation of this work is that, as the respondents for the interviews

Fig. 1. Interview and survey process and analysis, arranged by research objective.

and surveys on the islands are not closely representative of the islands' populations, it is difficult to determine if their responses are generalizable to the rest of their island's population (Bengtsson, 2016). Further, given the small number of participants compared to the populations of the islands, statistical interpretation was not deemed reasonable or appropriate. Additionally, both the interviews and surveys suffer from a self-selection bias, only volunteers to and participants in the REACT project were interviewed and surveyed. These participants can be reasonably expected to be those island residents most interested in the goals of the REACT project. Nonetheless, despite these limitations, by including actual users of energy transition technologies in different island situations and gathering their attitudes and experience before and after the use of such technologies allows the responses to remain valuable for both project and policy planning purposes (Stikvoort, et al., 2023).

3.1. Question development

The 19 questions developed for the initial interview sought to determine the respondent's starting points and early disposition toward energy usage and energy transition. Beyond the two questions asked to establish basic respondent demographics, five questions were posed to gain an understanding of the respondent's starting attitudes on activities and concepts related to energy transition that the REACT project would expose them to. An additional five questions sought to establish the respondent's level of awareness on the same activities and concepts.

Of the seven open-ended questions included in the interview, two sought to determine the source and depth of a respondent's awareness for the energy transition activities and concepts the REACT project pursued. An additional two questions asked what the respondent would like to learn more about the concepts and activities presented and a single question was posed to expand the understanding of the respondent's attitudes towards the examined concepts and activities. Another question asked about the respondent's concerns when using demand management technologies, a key element of the REACT project. The final question of the interview attempted to gain a level of understanding on the respondent's expectations around energy usage and energy transition (see Appendix A).

3.2. Interviews

Following the start of the REACT project, a semi-structured interview was first employed prior to or shortly after the installation of renewable energy technologies on and in the participant's residential or governmental building as part of the REACT project in which they were participating. These participant interviews sought to gather information on the participant's knowledge around and attitudes towards energy usage as well as familiarity with the key REACT energy solution and concepts of demand response, energy saving, energy management, local energy communities and energy storage.

This initial interview sought to determine the participants' starting points and early disposition toward energy transition and consisted of 19 questions, as explained in Section 3.1. The same questions were translated from a base English version into the local language of the Pilot island, Spanish and Italian, so that each participant was interviewed in their native language. The questions, regardless of language, were asked in the same order. Guidance was provided to the persons conducting the interviews regarding when follow-up questions should be asked.

The interviews took place between December 2020 and June 2021 on all three REACT Pilot islands and, due to the prevailing CoVid-19 conditions and travel restrictions, were conducted telephonically and using digital meeting options such as Zoom. The interviews lasted between a half hour and one hour.

The interview questions were reviewed by the REACT project ethics committee to confirm appropriate actions, in line with local and EU directives (Regulation (EU) 2016/679, 2016; ALLEA, 2023; Regulation

(EU) 2021/695, 2021; European Commission, 2016), were taken with regards to both the gathering and handling of all collected data. Explicit oral or written consent was obtained from each respondent to use data provided in the REACT project as a condition of their participation in the project. The base English template for the interviews can be found in Appendix A.

The interviews were collected in a word processing software and the results were then translated to English, as needed, before being transferred to a spreadsheet software to conduct comparative frequency analysis of the responses across the islands to determine what, if any, differences existed between them. For the open questions, conceptual content analysis was used to establish and organize the meanings behind repeating concepts and to analyze participants' expressed awareness so conclusions could be drawn from the responses (Carley, 1993; Bengtsson, 2016), see Section 4.1.2.

Not all island project participants agreed to be interviewed or chose to complete the surveys. In Table 1, each island's total participant number is shown, followed by the number of that total that choose to take part in each of the listed activities. In total, 17 interviews took place on the island of Inis Mór, 14 on La Graciosa and 17 on San Pietro.

3.3. Technology Acceptance Model

Determining users' experience towards a piece of technology is valuable, for among other reasons, in helping with its development and continued usage and the TAM is among the most common methods to gather this information. The TAM helps to find a perceived attitude towards a technology using a pair of criteria, usefulness and ease of use. If a person provides positive responses on both these criteria for a technology it is presumed they will use that technology (Davis, 1989). The TAM, has been applied to determine attitudes towards different types of software (Farhan, et al., 2019; Pal and Vanijja, 2020; Williams, 2021; Barney, et al., 2023) evaluate attitudes on different energy production technologies (Kardooni, et al., 2016; Tsaour and Lin, 2018; Malik and Ayop, 2020) various smart energy technologies (Billanes and Enevoldsen, 2021), smart homes (Hubert, et al., 2019) and electrical heating (Liu, et al., 2022), among others.

A year and a half after the completion of the interviews, allowing the participants to have an opportunity to use the REACT solution, an adapted TAM for the REACT project was sent to the same group of participants, see Appendix B. This adapted TAM sought to explore the participants' perceptions on the REACT solution installed in their homes or other buildings, such as solar panels, heat pumps and/or batteries, and to gauge their satisfaction with the solution and their intention to continue to use it. To do so, participants were asked to respond to statements by selecting the option most reflective of their agreement to that statement on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

The adapted TAM consisted of 25 questions. These questions fall into categories on respondent demographics (3), perceived usefulness of the REACT solution (4), perceived ease of use of the REACT solution (4), participant's attitude towards using the REACT solution (5), participant's intention to use the REACT solution (5) and open-ended questions related to social media usage and personal comfort (4). As with the interview, the same questions were translated from an English version into the local language of the Pilot island so that each participant was interviewed in their native language. The questions, regardless of

Table 1
Participants, by Pilot and activity.

	Inis Mór	La Graciosa	San Pietro
Island total participant number:	20	20	30
Total interviews conducted	17	14	17
Number TAM respondents	8	14	11
Number SUS respondents	8	12	6

language, were asked in the same order.

The TAM surveys took place between January 2023 and June 2023 on all three REACT Pilot islands. All those that received the TAM were participants in the REACT Pilot deployments. In total, eight TAM surveys were answered by participants on the island of Inis Mór, 14 on La Graciosa and 11 on San Pietro (Table 1).

3.4. System Usability Scale

The SUS was first widely presented in the mid-1990's to evaluate usability (Brooke, 1996). The standard formulation of SUS uses an alternating pattern of positive and negative wording for 10 usability statements. The respondent is presented with a five-point Likert scale, which the respondent uses to indicate to what extent they agree with the statement. The scores from the responses to these 10 statements are then combined to determine both the objective usability and the respondent's perceived usability and give scores which range from 0 to 100, with higher scores indicating better usability (Brooke, 1996, 2013) and a score of 68 generally being considered to mean 'average' usability (Lewis, 2018). Since its development, SUS has been used, and adapted (Martins, et al., 2015; Gronier and Baudet, 2021), for a range of applications (Kortum and Bangor, 2013; Pal and Vanijja, 2020) and is considered a reliable method for measuring of usability (Bangor, et al., 2008; Lewis, 2018).

A SUS survey was given to the REACT Pilot participants shortly after the TAM. The SUS survey was targeted at the perceived usability of the developed REACT information management software. The software under evaluation was available as an app for smartphones or tablets using the Android mobile operating system or via a webpage. The developed app provided information on the installations in the participants' homes and, among other uses, was designed to allow them to better adjust their energy consumption behaviors. Guides on how to use the developed software were provided via a YouTube channel in the languages of the different Pilot islands, see Fig. 2 below.

The standard SUS questions (Brooke, 1996) were used for the English variant while a Spanish and Italian translation of it were also used. All three variants included an additional open question in the survey's language which asked what the participant appreciated most about the software. The survey also included an open question allowing the participant to provide additional comments.

In total, eight SUS surveys were answered by participants on the

island of Inis Mór, 12 on La Graciosa and six on San Pietro (Table 1).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Interview results and discussion

In total 48 participants on the islands took part in the interviews out of 70 total participants in the project. Nearly all of the 20 participants on the island of Inis Mór took part and a majority of the participants on the other two islands. The following identifiers for respondents are used in the following subsections:

- IM## - Inis Mór participant and response number
- LG## - La Graciosa participant and response number
- SP## - San Pietro participant and response number

4.1.1. Respondent energy attitudes

The first five questions of the interview sought to gather information on the participants' perceptions towards concepts such as demand response, saving and managing energy, local energy communities and energy storage. Related responses to these questions can be found in Appendix C.

For activities such as demand response several participants across the three islands expressed interest and awareness. A sizeable portion, however, also stated they didn't know about demand response, with the majority of these being on Inis Mór. For the activities/concepts of saving and managing energy, nearly every participant was aware of them in some manner and expressed positivity towards them. Further, several participants on all three islands directly connected energy saving to economic savings in some way.

For the question regarding local energy communities, it is clear that the participants on Inis Mór and San Pietro were already aware of them, with only a few participants stating they didn't know. About half of the participants on La Graciosa, on the other hand, said they didn't know about them. The final question of the attitudes section of the interview inquired about how the participants thought about energy storage. All participants on La Graciosa and San Pietro were aware of it to some extent and the San Pietro participants expressed positivity towards it while the La Graciosa residents largely explained what they believed it to be. A third of the participants on Inis Mór stated they were unaware of energy storage but several linked learning about it to the project.

Fig. 2. YouTube frame from the demo video of the REACT software.

4.1.2. Energy transition concept and activity awareness

The next set of questions seeks to understand how much the participants know about the same concepts and activities that they were asked to express their perceptions on in the first set of questions. The participants were then given the opportunity to explain what they knew and many took advantage of this by detailing either what they knew about the concepts or activities in question as well as how they were applying them.

In line with responses to the first set of questions, participants on Inis Mór were the least aware of demand response while participants from San Pietro were the most familiar with it. None of the residents from La Graciosa felt they knew more than ‘Something’ about demand response while both Inis Mór and San Pietro had participants that believed themselves to be very knowledgeable about it, see Fig. 3 below.

Nearly all participants on the three islands knew ‘A little bit’ about saving energy, and a majority of the participants from San Pietro felt they knew a great deal about it, see Fig. 4.

Awareness of the concept of energy management, when compared to saving energy, is substantially lower and is about the same across the three islands. Again, participants from San Pietro felt they were the most familiar, but by a much lower margin, see Fig. 5 below.

While the majorities of the participants on both Inis Mór and San Pietro knew at least ‘A little bit’ about local energy communities, nearly two-thirds of participants on La Graciosa knew nothing, see Fig. 6.

Awareness of energy storage among the participants was similar across the islands, though La Graciosa participants were again the most likely to state they were not aware of it at all, see Fig. 7 below.

4.1.3. Open-ended questions

The final set of questions were open-ended and related to energy transition generally. One question asked where the participant learned about energy communities, given that they had heard about them before. On the island of Inis Mór nearly all stated they had found out about them from the local development co-op, on the island of San Pietro the majority stated they’d learned about them from the REACT project. On the island of La Graciosa, nearly all stated they had not heard about them but one stated they’d learned about them from the REACT project.

The participants were also asked to give the words or phrases that came to mind when they thought of demand response/energy saving/local energy communities. Participants often gave more than a single word or phrase and each phrase was counted. For example, a participant from La Graciosa stated they thought,

LG06 “Economic savings, improve the environment”

Each of these phrases were reviewed for commonalities and counted

separately before being placed into one of five key themes identified in the content analysis - energy, innovation, environment, economic savings and management. As can be seen in Fig. 8 below, references to economic savings occurred the most often. While some comment related to economic savings was invoked by participants on all islands, almost half of these came from La Graciosa and only a few less from Inis Mór. Energy related phrases were the next most likely to be occur, though none of the Inis Mór participants invoked a phrase using energy and the energy phrases were evenly split between the other two islands. Environmental phrases were invoked the next most frequently, more than half of by San Pietro’s participants. Terms related to innovation were used on all islands, while terms related to management were highlighted primarily by Inis Mór’s participants.

The participants were also asked about their concerns when using demand response. The single most common response was that the participant didn’t expect any issues, followed by concerns they don’t understand how to properly use the demand response system. The concern that they would not be able to properly use the demand response system was expressed mostly by participants on La Graciosa and Inis Mór. It was also the most common response from La Graciosa’s participants.

The final question in this section asked the participants to explain what they saw as the future trends in energy consumption. A wide range of answers were provided, with the most common terms in response were related to higher energy consumption, greater awareness of that consumption and usage of cleaner energy. San Pietro’s participants noted the trend of higher consumption most often while La Graciosa’s participants were the only ones to name cleaner energy and Inis Mór’s the only to see a trend of greater awareness of energy consumption.

4.1.4. Interview discussion

4.1.4.1. Respondent energy attitudes. The high levels of awareness for the concepts of saving and managing energy on all of the islands is useful as a starting point for engaging with and educating participants. This awareness provides a route by which island energy planners can introduce activities and tools which can facilitate both demand response and local energy communities. Further, the emphasis placed on the relationship between saving energy and saving money gives energy planners seeking to attract inhabitants to become involved in transition activities a clear means of doing so by emphasizing the financial benefits of those activities.

The positivity and interest found across the islands’ participants towards demand response is another encouraging sign for the testing and

Prior Awareness of Demand Response

Fig. 3. Participants’ prior awareness of the concept of demand response across the three islands.

Prior Awareness of Saving Energy

Fig. 4. Participants' prior awareness of the concept of saving energy across the three islands.

Prior Awareness of Energy Management

Fig. 5. Participants' prior awareness of the concept of energy management across the three islands.

Prior Awareness of Local Energy Communities

Fig. 6. Participants' prior awareness of the concept of local energy communities across the three islands.

Prior Awareness of Energy Storage

Fig. 7. Participants' prior awareness of the concept of energy storage across the three islands.

Words and phrases invoked by demand response/energy saving/local energy communities

Fig. 8. Words and phrases invoked by demand response/energy saving/local energy communities totals for the three islands.

implementation of demand response technologies, in particular on Inis Mór where nearly half of the participants stated they were not aware of what demand response was.

IM01 *"I feel it would be a good idea but I do not know anything about it."*

The high levels of awareness of, and general positivity towards, local energy communities on two of the three islands is also worth noting, especially in consideration with how the participants learned about them. On the island of Inis Mór the local energy co-op was clearly instrumental in spreading awareness of them while on the island of San Pietro it was the REACT project's outreach activities that informed them. A similar finding for the role of the REACT project in increasing awareness of energy transition technologies on Inis Mór was found, where the project's goals and activities were linked to learning about batteries and in turn spreading information about batteries.

IM07 *"Will be doing more of this now that we are involved in this project."*

4.1.4.2. *Energy transition concept and activity awareness.* Excepting demand response, the participants from La Graciosa, on average, reported themselves to be the least aware of the different activities and concepts for the REACT project, though participants from Inis Mór reported they

knew the least about demand response. San Pietro's participants were the most familiar overall with the different activities and concepts, excluding saving energy, though not by a large margin.

4.1.4.3. *Open-ended questions.* The close link made by participants on all three islands for the key REACT energy transition activities and economic benefits, is in line with other research, particularly for demand response (Broman Toft, et al., 2014; Karadooni, et al., 2016; Naghiyev, et al., 2022; Barney, et al., 2023). The other most common phrases connected to the energy transition activities seem to indicate differing local attitudes towards energy transition, with economic benefits being of greater apparent concern on La Graciosa and Inis Mór than San Pietro. Conversely, environmental benefits were more closely linked to the activities on San Pietro than the other two islands and management and ownership were more associated with them on Inis Mór. Where a participant learned about the REACT project's key concepts first had no clear impact on their associations with those concepts.

The concern most commonly noted by respondents in this study, i.e., that they would be unable to use the demand response system, is similar to that found in other research as concerns around ease of use (Parrish, et al., 2020). Other common concerns research on demand response,

such as loss of control and data security, were not reflected in the concerns of the project’s participants that took part in survey (Murtagh, et al., 2014; Barney, et al., 2023) (Murtagh, et al., 2014; Barney, et al., 2023). Instead, concerns related to the difficulty in getting repairs and maintenance done on islands and supply adequacy were named.

IM17 “Any breakdown issues on the island might be a problem waiting for someone to fix it.”

SP04 “Maintenance when there are problems.”

The final question on what participants saw as the future trends in energy consumption indicate different starting points in perspectives on the islands. These different starting perspectives, together with other local associations on each island, such as the greater focus on ownership, can be used by planners to adjust their plans and messaging to attract further participants.

4.2. TAM results and discussion

Of the 70 participants in the REACT project, 33 took part in the TAM survey with a majority from La Graciosa (Table 1). Additional review of each island’s TAM responses can be found in Appendix D.

4.2.1. Inis Mór results

The eight participants on Inis Mór expressed largely positive overall attitudes towards the systems installed in their dwelling or other building, all but one agreeing that these systems were both useful and easy to use. The one individual which did not ‘Agree’ gave the system a neutral rating.

The additional free text responses on the TAM survey showed that most participants did not use the project’s social media accounts, despite nearly all being active on social media generally. The responses also showed varied convenience requirements, though a majority included heating as a requirement.

4.2.2. La Graciosa results

The fourteen (14) participants on La Graciosa also expressed largely positive attitudes towards the system installed in their dwelling or other building, but three participants were less positive to that the systems were both useful and easy to use. These three participants were not, however, in agreement over what they perceived as not being useful or easy to use about the system and in several cases gave responses on opposite ends of the scale for different questions.

The free text responses showed, similar to Inis Mór, most participants did not visit or join the project’s social media though, unlike Inis Mór, most were also not active on social media.

4.2.3. San Pietro results

The 11 participants from San Pietro, like on the other two islands, expressed largely positive attitudes towards the systems installed in their dwelling or other building though one participant gave the system a slightly negative overall rating, the only to do so on the three islands.

The free text responses showed, similar to the other islands, most did not visit or join the project’s social media though, like in La Graciosa, most were not active on social media.

4.2.4. Comparison of results

The responses on the TAM from the islands show that the San Pietro participants’ attitudes towards the system were, on average, the most positive while the La Graciosa participants were the least, see Fig. 9. Further, all islands saw lower scores around the ease of use of the system as evidenced by the responses on Questions 5 through 8 and higher scores for the usefulness of the systems, particularly for questions 12, 16 and 18.

4.2.5. TAM discussion

Taken as a whole, the TAM surveys indicate a moderately positive perceived attitude overall to the REACT project’s solutions across the three islands. When considered in more detail, it is clear that the project’s demand response app, despite being widely considered useful on all islands, struggled with its ease of use. This could pose a problem for the app’s ability to attract and keep users since, as noted above, ease of use is key for users when considering whether or not to use demand response software (Broman Toft, et al., 2014; Kardooni, et al., 2016; Naghiyev, et al., 2022).

These ease-of-use issues were considered most significant by participants on the islands of Inis Mór and La Graciosa, which matches the concerns given by the participants on those islands during the interviews of not being able to use the demand response system. It is difficult to assess how much prior concerns of the participants influenced the subsequent perceived ease of use of the app but it does appear to have had an impact and should have been addressed during the app’s development.

From the interviews it can be seen that San Pietro’s participants felt they were the most familiar with the project’s concepts and activities and they were also the most positive overall towards the system in the TAM survey. Like on La Graciosa, it is difficult to determine how much prior familiarity with and perceptions of project concepts impacted San Pietro’s participants’ attitudes towards the system. That said, it does appear to have had some impact which is in line with other research showing that both awareness and knowledge influence the acceptance and adaptation of technologies (Billanes and Enevoldsen, 2021).

Fig. 9. Comparison of participant average responses to the TAM survey questions; question sets grouped.

4.3. SUS results and discussion

There were 22 completed participant responses to the SUS survey with only a majority of participants taking part from the island of La Graciosa.

4.3.1. Inis Mór results

The combined SUS score for the project app from the participants on Inis Mór was 62.8, which is considered below average usability. The free text comments on what the participant felt was the best functionality from the app, along with other open comments, lifted issues beyond those with the app.

IM6: *I don't have the app yet so I don't really know how it's working, and as far as I am aware my battery hasn't been working properly ever.*

4.3.2. La Graciosa results

The final SUS score for La Graciosa was 57.7, indicating an even lower user experience than that experienced on Inis Mór. The free text comments on what the participant felt was the best functionality from the app ranged from some feeling the app could be made simpler to that it was already simple to use.

LG25: *(It could be) a little more simple, or more help to be able to understand it a little bit better.*

LG04: *Its simplicity.*

In the free comments, a few participants thought the app could be improved by adding iOS support.

4.3.3. San Pietro results

For San Pietro, the final SUS score for the app was 82.0, a good experience and significantly higher than the user experience from the other two islands. The comments on what the participants felt was the best functionality from the app and the other free text responses included suggestions on ways to improve user experience further.

4.3.4. Comparison

The SUS scores obtained from participants on Inis Mór and La Graciosa indicate a below average user experience with the project's demand response app, while the scores from San Pietro indicate an above average experience. The participants from San Pietro were, on average, notably more positive towards the software on every question except the first, see Fig. 10 below.

4.3.5. SUS discussion

In line with the results of the TAM survey, the SUS findings show a below average user experience on two of the three islands. Of particular

interest, however, is the scale of difference between these two islands and the above average experience of participants on San Pietro. Considering that, other than language, the app was identical for all three islands, and performed similarly in the TAM survey, the substantially better experience on San Pietro can be seen as being remarkably good. Considering the SUS survey results alongside the interview results, potentially indicates that the residents' relatively higher early awareness potentially translated to better app useability. It is possible that the early concerns on La Graciosa and Inis Mór expressed by participants about the ease of use, as well as the lack of awareness of demand response generally, possibly negatively influenced their user experiences.

Further, some users on Inis Mór had experience with another commercial application with similar functionality to that provided by the REACT project. These users compared the two applications and expressed a preference for the commercial application's usability and functionality over the REACT project's, which is potentially reflected in the SUS scores they provided.

4.4. Overview of interview and surveys

The survey conducted prior to the start of project activities (Abi Ghanem and Crosbie, 2021), showed that significant portions of the populations on each of the three considered islands were unaware of key energy transition concepts. Significant numbers of respondents on all three islands, in many cases majorities, were largely unaware of technologies related to or enabling energy transition, such smart meters and home energy management systems. Despite this lack of awareness, respondents on all three islands indicated strong degrees of willingness to participate. These high levels of positivity before the installation of the REACT solution are also reflected in the initial interviews of the project's participants, as are the low overall levels of awareness. The interviews done in this paper confirm the earlier survey results which is potentially useful to planners, especially given that it seems to be able to, under certain circumstances at least, exist without full understanding of what is going to take place.

It is therefore interesting to note that despite knowing of the low levels of participant awareness before technologies were installed, the TAM survey results indicate participants still found the installed systems to be less than easy to use. The SUS survey shows similar results for the control software, with the exception of on San Pietro, where respondents indicated a need to learn things to be able to use the software and that they had needed support to use it. These difficulties in using the installed technologies and software appear to indicate at least a level of missed opportunity by the REACT project to fully take into account the

Fig. 10. Comparison of participant average responses to the SUS survey questions; question sets grouped.

awareness starting points of the users for the systems installed and the designed control software. Understanding this, the design of the software is of clear importance and time should be invested to make it more user friendly. Despite this shortfall, participants on all islands maintained their willingness to continue to engage with energy transition activities even given their sometimes less than positive experiences with the project solution.

Some amount of improvement to participant's experiences could also have potentially been gained by the REACT project providing additional information to participants at an early stage. This is particularly the case when a participant names the project as their primary or initial source of information for the concepts and technologies to be installed, as was done by several participants in their interview responses.

It must also be considered that the decreasing participation in the TAM and SUS surveys from the initial interviews could have potentially influenced the results. This is particularly the case for San Pietro where only slightly more than half of the island's project participants took part in the interviews and fewer than quarter took part in the SUS survey. It is entirely possible the island's high SUS score would have been more in line with the other islands had additional responses been received from more of the users of the app on the island. Additionally, it is important to recognize again that the respondents involved in both the TAM and SUS surveys as well as the interview were from a group of individuals who had actively chosen to join a project that dealt directly with island energy transition and management. This group represents a "best-case scenario" sample of interested and motivated users (Stikvoort, et al., 2023) on these islands. That said, valuable information can still be drawn from their responses, taken both before and after being exposed to core energy transition technologies. In particular, how the noted initial concerns and subsequent usage difficulties for a motivated individual would impact the experience and involvement of islanders, and other individuals more generally, who are less engaged with energy management and transition.

To that end, while the results of this work offer valuable insights, future studies should seek to include a larger, more diverse set of island residents in the initial interview stage to gain a wider understanding of islanders' awareness and attitudes towards key energy transition activities and their perceptions of different transition technologies. It is, however, not reasonably possible to obtain responses from non-participants to gauge the impacts this initial awareness had on their interactions with specific energy transition tools and technologies outside of a project setting.

5. Conclusions

In this article, residents on three islands of the EU Horizon 2020 REACT project were interviewed and surveyed first in relation to their initial knowledge and understanding of basic energy transition concepts, methods and activities and then in regards to their actual experience of using energy transition technologies and software installed at their homes or buildings they managed. The responses from the interviews and surveys were considered first on an island-by-island basis before then being used to compare across the three islands to develop more generalized conclusions on how initial awareness of, and attitudes

Appendix A. - Interview

Introduction

Welcome (don't forget to thank the person for answering the call, attending the appointment, etc.)

Introduce yourself

We will be talking about demand response, energy saving, energy management, local energy community, energy storage, and also briefly about some ethical issues.

The results will be used to inform the project and advance in the area of renewable energies and energy self-sufficient islands.

towards, energy transition concepts impacted user experiences with energy transition tools and technologies.

The interviews of participants showed that awareness of key energy concepts and energy transition tools was mixed. The same participants were followed up with on all islands using surveys after the REACT project's technology was installed and an app for controlling and monitoring that technology was developed and deployed to them. The responses from the follow up surveys indicate initial understandings of the project concepts and activities had impacted user experience, with islands that had lower understandings giving lower usability scores.

These findings, from before and during islanders' interactions with energy transition technologies and tools, underline the importance, for energy projects developers as well as for energy transition planners more generally, of knowing the starting points of potential participants in energy transition and incorporating those points into future plans. Evidently, knowing these points is only a starting point for determining what new information or training should be developed, but eventually this initial knowledge could be used to complement whatever changes can feasibly be made to the technology being deployed or activity being undertaken to address participant concerns. Concrete examples of this would be working to address any identified users' control and ease of use concerns directly with the impacted users. This paper's findings further highlight and confirm that addressing shortfalls in the participants' understandings with an aim of improving their experience with energy transition activities and technologies can, in turn, impact participants' willingness to continue engaging. Finally, it was found that highly motivated participants will continue to engage despite relatively lack-luster experiences. Integrating these findings, energy transition planners and energy project developers and managers can potentially enhance participants' experiences with transition activities and further foster long-term engagement.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Polatidis Heracles: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Barney Andrew:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Salces Fausto Sainz:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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You were selected because you are part of the project and you have some knowledge about the topics to be treated now.

Demographic data

Age.....Gender.....

Questions

What are your general feelings about ...
 demand response?
 energy saving?
 energy management?
 local energy communities?
 energy storage?

Do you know anything about demand response? (Interviewer: Please write down response, if possible, and adapt answer to the following scale)

Nothing	A little bit	Something	Quite a bit	A lot
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Do you know anything about energy saving? (Interviewer: Please write down response, if possible, and adapt answer to the following scale)

Nothing	A little bit	Something	Quite a bit	A lot
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Do you know anything about energy management? (Interviewer: Please write down response, if possible, and adapt answer to the following scale)

Nothing	A little bit	Something	Quite a bit	A lot
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Do you know anything about local energy communities? (Interviewer: Please write down response, if possible, and adapt answer to the following scale)

Nothing	A little bit	Something	Quite a bit	A lot
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Do you know anything about energy storage? (Interviewer: Please write down response, if possible, and adapt answer to the following scale)

Nothing	A little bit	Something	Quite a bit	A lot
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Is there something else you would like to learn more about?
 If so, what?
 Have you heard about local energy communities?
 If yes: How did you first hear about the local energy communities?
 What words or phrases come to mind when you think of:
 demand response?
 energy saving?
 local energy communities?
 Are you familiar with the concepts of:
 demand response?
 energy saving?
 local energy communities?
 If yes: When, how, and where do you use this technology?

What do you like or would like to know about this technology that helps you manage energy demand in your home or workplace?
 What are your problems or concerns when using this energy solution (demand response)?
 What trends do you see happening in the energy consumption?

Appendix B. - TAM Survey

Demographic data

Age Gender..... Participant.....

Questions

Please state your opinion with the statements below. On a scale from 1 to 7 where 1 reflects that you strongly disagree with the statement and 7 that you strongly agree with it.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7				
Strongly disagree	Disagree	Slightly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Slightly agree	Agree	Strongly agree				
				1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Perceived Usefulness										
Q1. Using the REACT Demand Response software would help me control the energy consumption.										
Q2. Using the energy response units controller enhances energy saving.										
Q3. I find the energy control system useful in my daily energy control.										
Q4. Using REACT control devices makes it easier to catch individual energy needs.										
Perceived Ease of Use										
Q5. It is easy to become skilful at using the REACT interface.										
Q6. I find it easy to apply the Demand Response energy controller in my home.										
Q7. Using the REACT Demand Response control tools is easy and understandable.										
Q8. Using REACT Demand Response control tools is more flexible to teach than traditional ones.										
Attitude Toward Using										
Q9. Using energy management tool at home is good.										
Q10. Using the REACT Demand Response control system at home is favourable.										
Q11. It is a positive influence for me to use REACT Demand Response control system at home.										
Q12. I think it is valuable to use REACT Demand Response control system at home.										
Q13. I think it is a trend to use a Demand Response control system at home.										
Intention to Use										
Q14. I tend to use a Demand Response control system in my home.										
Q15. I increase the occurrences of using Demand Response control system in my home.										
Q16. Using a Demand Response control system in my home enhances energy savings interest.										
Q17. I'd love to use REACT Demand Response control system in my home.										
Q18. I use a Demand Response control system to provide a greener approach on energy consumption.										

Have you used the REACT La Graciosa Facebook/WhatsApp (delete as appropriate) group?
 How have you used social media in your daily life?
 What have been your comfort/convenience preferences/requirements in reference to your home?
 How have you managed to meet your comfort/convenience goals?

Appendix C. – Interview Free Text Responses

The following identifiers for respondents are used in this Appendix
 IM## - Inis Mór participant and response number
 LG## - La Graciosa participant and response number
 SP## - San Petro participant and response number
 Free text interview responses related to demand response:
 IM05 “I feel this is a good thing where we change our habits and thus save money and the environment.”
 LG12 “Positive. No need for a central electricity supply.”
 SP33 “Great idea, solves many issues related to consumption during the day!”
 Free text interview responses related to the activities/concepts of saving and managing energy:
 IM10 “Very important for the environment.”
 LG15 “To know how to make good use of energy.”
 SP37 “Very interested, I would like to be more aware about my consumptions in order to monitor them and try to reduce them.”
 IM10 “The cost of electricity is rising each day and this will be beneficial to our savings”

LG15 “To know how to use energy to save economically.”

SP09 “Connecting to the previous answers: having a better energy management, I believe it will lead to an improvement of the environment, as well as savings.”

Free text interview responses related to energy communities:

IM17 “These are a great idea! I think ... it gives everyone an appreciation that the more that (are) involved the better for everyone.”

SP47 “I think it’s a step towards saving energy and therefore reducing pollution. The way the cost of energy is going up, being self-sufficient is a step towards saving.”

Free text interview responses related to energy storage:

LG14 “Saving energy to use it later.”

SP39 “It would be a good thing, ... it would allow me to have a back-up during blackouts”

IM07 “Will be doing more of this now that we are involved in this project.”

Appendix D. – TAM Survey Data

5.1. Inis Mór results

On the first four questions of the TAM survey, which asked about the perceived usefulness of the systems, all of the participants agreed the systems were useful. This agreement from all participants on the systems did not extend to the second set of questions about the systems’ ease of use. Most participants only slightly agreed that the system was easy to use and one was neutral to its use. The third set of questions on the actual usefulness of the system was less positive than its perceived usefulness, but most of the participants agreed the system was useful and only a single participant was neutral to its usefulness. The final set of questions on the participants’ intentions to use the system were positive, again with all but one participant agreeing or strongly agreeing that they would use the system. An average of the responses for each question for the island of Inis Mór can be seen below in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Inis Mór participants’ average responses to the TAM survey questions; question sets grouped

La Graciosa results

On the first four questions of the TAM survey on the perceived usefulness of the system, 12 participants agreed with the perception that the system was useful and the remaining two were neutral to its perceived usefulness. There was a noticeable drop in the number of participants that agreed that the system was easy to use in the second set of questions, with only half of participants agreeing that it was. Of the remaining seven participants, three were neutral towards the system’s ease of use and the rest felt the system was not easy to use, one strongly so. The responses to the questions on the participants’ actual use of the system were similar to those on perceived usefulness, most of the participants agreed the system was useful, a pair were neutral to its usefulness and one strongly disagreed that the system was useful. The final questions on the participants’ intentions to use the system were positive, particularly for the last three questions. Two participants were neutral to using the system while the rest were positive to using the system. An average of the responses for each question for the island of La Graciosa can be seen below in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. La Graciosa participants’ average responses to the TAM survey questions; question sets grouped

5.2. San Pietro results

On the perceived usefulness of the system questions, 10 participants agreed with the perception that the system was useful while one was neutral to its perceived usefulness. As with the other islands, there was a noticeable, though less significant, drop in the number of participants that agreed that the system was easy to use. Two participants felt the system was not easy to use while the remaining nine did. The answers on the participants’ actual use of the system were more positive than the perceived usefulness with all participants agreeing the system was useful. The remaining questions on the participants’ intentions to use the system were also positive, especially the final three questions. One participant was neutral to using the system and one was negative while the rest were positive. An average of the responses for each question for the island of San Pietro can be seen below in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. San Pietro participants’ average responses to the TAM survey questions; question sets grouped

Data Availability

The datasets used in this paper are stored in and available from the Zenodo repository.

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